

Figure 1: RIG-I induced NK-cell cytotoxicity differs between tumor cell types.

(a) Schematic representation of NK cytotoxicity assay with RIG-I stimulation of target cells and gating strategy used to determine % specific lysis. TA: control wells with only target cells, AW: Assay wells with specific effector-to-target (E:T) ratio. (b, c) NK cytotoxicity after 20 h-coculture with Capan-2, A-431, EFO-21, HT-29, and SK-OV-3 cells previously stimulated with RIG-I ligand (3p-dsRNA) or a control RNA (3p-ssRNA). Cocultures with expanded primary NK cells (b, Mean ± SD specific lysis from at least 5 NK donors at different E:T ratios are shown) or NK-92 cells (c, Mean ± SD specific lysis from at least 4 independent experiments at different E:T ratios are shown). (d) Type I interferon (IFN-I) activity in supernatants from wells with target cells alone in the cocultures, tested in HEK-Blue Reporter Cells, expressed as IFNα2a equivalent units (EqU, n=4). (e) RIG-I activity in tumor cell lines as measured by IFN-I production (X = IFN-I not detected, check mark = IFN-I production) and NK cytotoxicity after RIG-I stimulation on target cells is summarized on the table for all cell lines included in the study: = represents no differences in NK cytotoxicity, for increases in specific lysis: (+) < 5 %, + 5-10 %, ++ 10-20 %, +++ > 20 %, n.s. statistically not significant. Abbreviations: Chronic Myeloid Leukemia (CML), Squamous Cell Carcinoma (SCC), Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC), Colorectal Cancer (CRC), Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinoma (PDAC), Ovarian Serous Cystadenocarcinoma (OSCC), and Osteogenic Sarcoma (OGS). Statistical comparisons were performed using two-way ANOVA with matched donors and Šidák's (b, c) post-hoc test. *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.005, ****p < 0.001.